

Prevalence of hepatitis B virus infection among health care workers in Sudan

Ahmed Y.A.¹, Ali Y.H.^{2,3}, Abdellatif M.M.², Intisar K.S.^{2,3}, Amani A.A.⁴

¹ College of Medical Laboratory Science, University of Sudan.

² Department of Biology, College of Science and Arts, Rafha, Northern Border University, Arar, Saudi Arabia.

³ Virology Department, Central Veterinary Research Laboratory, P.O. Box 8067, Khartoum, Sudan

⁴ Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, College of Pharmacy, Rafha, Northern Border University, Arar, Saudi Arabia.

Abstract

Hepatitis B infection is a major disease affecting humans worldwide. Diagnosis of the disease is mainly through the detection of virus antigen, antibodies and nucleic acid. The disease is known to be endemic in Sudan. This study aimed to estimate the incidence of hepatitis B infection in Sudan through analyzing data of HBV and jaundice patients during 2005-2008 and sero-monitoring of HBsAg among health care workers at Khartoum State. According to analyzed data state and age groups, highest seroprevalence was observed in Khartoum State (53.3%) then Darfur (19%) mostly among patients over 45 years of age (99.9%). Chi-square analysis revealed significant correlation between hepatitis B infection and the state ($p=0.000$) and age group ($p=0.000$). Sera ($n=100$) collected from health care workers were tested for HBsAg using ELISA. The virus Ag was detected (4%) in samples from lab technician and assistants. Infected workers wear gloves during the work, not vaccinated and no injury was recorded.

HBV infection is widely spread in Sudan. Immunization and strict preventive measures should be adopted to protect medical field workers from contracting the virus.

Keywords: Hepatitis B, Jaundice Patients, Healthcare workers, HBsAg-ELISA, Sudan

Introduction

Infectious hepatitis is caused mainly by one of three viruses: hepatitis A, hepatitis B and hepatitis C virus. Sometimes, hepatitis B or C infection can destroy the liver, resulting in a need for liver transplant for the patient's survival [1]. Hepatitis B virus (HBV) is known to cause severe liver diseases, chronic hepatitis, cirrhosis, carcinoma [2]. The infection is caused by HBV, a partially double-stranded DNA virus of a small viral genome, classified in the Hepadnaviridae family [3]. Estimated chronic HBV infections worldwide is 296 million. It is the leading cause of liver cirrhosis with estimated 331,000 deaths and 192,000 cancer deaths in 2019 [4].

Hepatitis B infection is prevalent throughout the world, particularly in Asia. HBV chronically infected patients globally are around three hundred million, about 75% of them are Asian, where a high incidence of hepatocellular carcinoma is reported in different Asian countries [5]. Seventy five percent of the global viral hepatitis burden is encountered in twenty countries, ten of them are in Asia [1]. Within patients with cirrhosis, prevalence of HBV infection in Africa and Asia was higher than in Europe, Americas and Oceania [6]. HBV was detected in a wide range of individuals, 0.87% to 21.4% in India [7], 7% in Pakistan [8]. Prevalence of HBV infection during 2018 - 2022 was 3% in China [9].

Health care workers (HCWs) are of the most probably exposed groups to the infection, In a study reviewing the existence of infection in HCWs in 71 countries over 54 years period, the pooled seroprevalences of total immunity against HBV was 57% and immunity acquired by natural HBV infection in HCWs was 9% [10]. In a care center in Saudi Arabia, healthcare workers were tested for IgG antibodies against 5 viral agents, hepatitis B was highest among healthcare workers from the Middle East [11].

HBV infection is endemic in sub-Saharan Africa, overall seroprevalence of 6% is estimated [12]. HBV was predominant in western Africa, Nigeria and Mali [6]. In Kenya, a study documented the importance of hepatitis B vaccination for HCWs where high exposure rates are associated with low levels of vaccine coverage [13]. The infection was reported in distinct groups in Ethiopia [14, 15], Egypt [16] and South Sudan [16], people suffering from viral hepatitis in Egypt are estimated to be 8–10 million [17].

In Sudan, several reports have documented the existence of HBV infection, HBVsAg was detected in 6% of 728 pregnant women tested in Khartoum State [18]. Seroprevalence varied from 47%–78% was detected [19], six percent of health care workers in Khartoum State tested positive for HBsAg [20]. Many Reports on HBV DNA detection were published, 36% of blood donors tested positive for HBV-DNA [21], in renal transplant recipients in Khartoum [22], among febrile patients in West Kordofan [23] and River Nile [24], among hemodialysis patients in Khartoum [25], White Nile [26], Darfur [27] and Gezira [28].

Sachdev et al. [29] reported that patients showing jaundice were positive for HBsAg. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the prevalence of HBV among patients with jaundice in Sudan, as well as to estimate the infection frequency among health care workers in Khartoum State.

Materials and method

Collection of data

Data about the incidence of hepatitis B among viral hepatitis and jaundice patients in Sudan during 2005-2008 were kindly provided by Ministry of Health. Processing and analysis of data was done using SPSS version 22 (Statistical Package for Social Sciences). Significance of differences was determined using Chi-square test and statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Ethical consideration

This work has been approved by the Ethical Committee of the Tropical Medicine Research Institute, Sudan Academy for Science.

Study population

This study was carried out during 2005 - 2008, recruiting healthcare workers (n =100) at Khartoum teaching hospital and National health laboratory, Sudan. Fifty female and 50 males, their occupations are, 7 physicians, 36 lab technicians, 10 cleaning staff, 20 lab. Attendants, 20 lab. assistants and 7 aid nurses were included in the study.

Collection of sera

Venous blood (5ml) was drawn under sterile conditions, from each subject (n=100). Sera was separated by centrifugation at 2000 rpm for 5min, stored at -20C° until tested. Sera were collected from health care workers at Khartoum State, location of the State is shown in Figure (1).

HBsAg-ELISA

An enzyme immunoassay for the detection of HBsAg (Siemens healthcare diagnostic, Marburg, Germany), was used according to the instructions provided by the manufacturer. Briefly, 100µl of serum, negative and positive controls were added to the microplate well, 25µl of conjugate was dispensed and the plate was incubated at 37°C for 60 min, the plate was washed 5 times with 350µl of washing solution, then 100µl of conjugate was added and the plate was placed for 30min, after washing, 75µl of chromogen was added. The reaction was stopped by the addition of 75µl stopping solution, read at 450nm.

Results

Epidemiology of Hepatitis B

According to the analyzed data, the highest prevalence of HBsAg were found in Khartoum state (53.3%), then Darfur (19%), age wise the infection was the higher among patients over 45 years of age (99.9%) (Figure 2, 3). Chi-square revealed a significant correlation between HBsAg and the state ($p=0.000$) and the age group ($p=0.000$).

Monitoring of HBVsAg

Out of one hundred sera tested, 4 (4%) were reactive by HBsAg-ELISA (Figure 4). Positive cases were among Assistant and lab technicians (Figure 5, Table 1). HBsAg carrier workers were wearing gloves during the work, not vaccinated and were not exposed to needle injury.

Figure 1: Map of Republic of Sudan showing Khartoum city where specimens from HCWs were tested for HBsAg.

Figure 2: Percentages of Hepatitis B infection among hepatic jaundice patients in Sudan according to states during 2005-2008 based on data provided by Ministry of Health.

Figure 3: Prevalence of Hepatitis B infection among hepatic jaundice patients in Sudan according to age during 2005-2008 based on data provided by Ministry of Health.

Figure 4: Seroprevalence of Hepatitis B infection among health care workers at Khartoum Teaching Hospital and National Health Laboratory as tested by HBsAg-ELISA.

Figure 5: prevalence of Hepatitis B according to profession at Khartoum Teaching Hospital and National Health Laboratory as tested by HBsAg-ELISA.

Table 1: Health care workers as tested by HBsAg-ELISA according to sex and profession at Khartoum teaching hospital and National health laboratory.

Sex	Male			Female			Total
Count	50			50			100
%	50			50			
Profession	physician	lab. technicians	cleaning staff	10 lab. Attendant	lab.assistant	aid nurses	100
Count	7	36	10	20	20	7	100
%	7	36	10	20	20	7	100

Discussion

Hepatitis B virus infection is of worldwide distribution among different communities with variable age, sex and occupations. Seroprevalence rates varied among countries. Published work on HBV infection in Africa and Asia was reviewed, 5.0% seroprevalence of HBV was reported where higher estimates were in Africa than Asia, Highest pooled prevalence estimate in African countries (8.0%) were in Cameroon and the lowest (4.0%), was in Ethiopia [30]. During 1990 - 2019, Asia reported the largest acute viral hepatitis burden in the five continents worldwide, Georgia, Qatar and UAE, still facing severe acute hepatitis burden [31]. In a collection of studies in India, the overall prevalence of HBV ranged between 0.87% - 21.4% [7], in Kenya it was 10% in Nairobi [32] and 1 – 5% [32], 7.4% in Ethiopia [14], 11% in pregnant women in Juba, South Sudan [33]. Hepatitis B surface antigen was detected in 7% in central Sudan and 26% in southern Sudan [19]. In Khartoum, 10% of screened persons were positive for HBV antibodies [34].

From the analyzed data in this study, prevalence of HBV was higher in Khartoum State, then Darfur, this is in agreement with the reports documented the prevalence using viral DNA detection in Sudan previously reviewed [35]. This is most probably due to the high population density in both States beside the existence of some more areas with people of low income and educational level.

The most affected age group in Sudan was found to be at 45 years and above, almost the same picture was observed in many countries, The mean age of HBV patients in study populations was 43–56 years in South-Central Asian countries, 39–52 years in sub-Saharan Africa and 54–63 years in South America [6]. However, slightly different results were reported in Sudan where the 30-49 years age group represents 58.4% of the subjects, then less than 30 age group (30.7%), while it was only 11% for more than 50 years

age [20]. Unlike our results, highest prevalence was reported at 24–39 age group in Ethiopia [14] and at age ≥ 18 years in China [9], in early middle age in Egypt [16].

Marked disparities were documented in Kenya at (93 %), Mombasa at (81.8 %), Nairobi (34 %) [32]. The prevalence of HBV among patients with hepatic jaundice reported by Al-Shami [36] was 7%, and the highest rate was in patients of 11-20 years (18%). The discrepancies could be attributed to differences in the patient population seeking medical attention between locations. Environmental or infectious factors other than viral hepatitis that cause jaundice, such as malaria and other parasite illnesses, may also be implicated.

HCWs are at substantial risk for the infection, published work within this category in 71 countries, during 1964 - 2019 were reviewed. The pooled seroprevalence of current HBsAg, was 2% and acute HBV infection was 5% [10].

In this study, Seroprevalence of HBVsAg was 4% in examined HCWs, this is lower than the prevalence obtained (6%) in Khartoum [20], far higher seroprevalence of hepatitis B virus (43%) was detected in foreign healthcare workers in Saudi Arabia, it was highest among HCWs from the Middle East [37]. In USA, HBV infection prevalence rates of 13 - 18% have been detected in surgeons, and up to 27% in dentists and oral surgeons [38]. In Brazil, 11% of dentists tested were seropositive for HBsAg [39]. Lower prevalence (2.4%) was detected in HCWs in Korea [40]. Much lower prevalence rate of 1% for HBsAg was recorded in HCWs in Delhi [41], among Egyptians 1.1% [42] and about 1.5% [17], while none of dental workers, found to be HBsAg positive in Japan [43].

HBV is common among hepatic jaundice patients in Sudan. The disease's prevalence, clinical manifestations, and distribution must be investigated. It is recommended that HCWs have to be immunized, as about 24% of the HCWs around the world are not vaccinated [44]. The United States, recommend the vaccination of clinical and nonclinical health center staff against hepatitis B [45].

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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